

Graphic notation and the Mind: Cognitive, Psychological and Physiological Mechanisms of Graphic Score Performance

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This paper presents a theoretical framework for understanding the neurocognitive mechanisms involved in reading graphic notation, drawing on findings from notation perception, cognitive load theory, symbol recognition, and cross-modal perception. A cognitive model for performing with graphic and animated scores is proposed, investigating how scores shape performers' interpretive decisions, attention, and embodied gestures. An ongoing mixed-methods study combining biometric, behavioral, and qualitative measures tests performers' reactions to systematically manipulated scores varying in visual complexity, spatial layout, and animation timing. The research reveals that graphic scores are not inherently more difficult than conventional notation; rather, difficulties emerge when compositional parameters push visual complexity, density, and overlap beyond performers' cognitive capacity. Preliminary findings indicate that while high-density, overlapping scores increase stress and error rates, participants consistently experienced heightened cognitive demands as positive, creative engagement rather than frustration. Case studies demonstrate that graphic notation encourages inclusivity and creativity, enabling performance without conventional notation barriers, particularly benefiting children and amateur musicians. By integrating neurocognitive research with compositional and pedagogical practice, this paper argues that graphic notation should be regarded not merely as artistic expression but as a domain for interdisciplinary research and pedagogical innovation, with the potential to revitalize contemporary music education and performance.

Keywords: Graphic Notation, Notation Perception, Neurocognition, Graphic Score Performance.

Contemporary notational practices, including graphic, animated, generative, and interactive forms offer unique artistic and pedagogical potential. Modern animated and graphic scores make use of new media and technologies (Hope 2017), as well as the performer's creative abilities, possibly more than conventional notation that has remained largely unchanged for almost 250 years (Fischer 2015). Graphic notation enables composers to explore new artistic avenues and is a tool for inclusive, interdisciplinary, and educational programs, not only because of its adaptability, but also because of its relatively low barrier of entry and possibilities for group-based educational work (Sawyer 2006). Even people who cannot read traditional notation can engage meaningfully with symbolic interpretation (Wiggins 2000).

Figure 1. Example of a 3D animated graphic score by the first author. Note the three objects that are moving in 3D space, each of which represents sound from one instrument.

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Despite a growing body of theoretical discourse and tool development, there is still relatively little empirical research on how musicians perceive, process, and perform graphic scores. Work that explicitly examines

neurocognitive and pedagogical dimensions, especially of graphic and animated notation performance, remains even more limited. Recent studies in pedagogy exist, and studies on children's self-generated graphical representations suggest substantial potential for musical sense-making and creativity (Nikolaou et al. 2024; Vidulin/Žižović 2024).

Many composers and performers tend to shy away from graphic notation, among other reasons, because of the lack of accessible scientific research and empirical information (Wimbish 2020). Negative or skeptical attitudes often arise from perfectionist performance cultures and assessment systems that reward error-free reproduction of conventional notation, while graphic scores are rarely addressed systematically in curricula and instead demand flexibility, negotiation, and shared authorship. As a result, graphic notation remains largely marginal in mainstream music education and professional practice, which restricts creative exploration, limits interpretive diversity, and reinforces a narrow definition of musical literacy and expertise. The first author's work responds to this situation by studying graphic notation and its influences and by developing pedagogical and empirical approaches that bring these notational forms closer to performers and composers.

RESEARCH QUESTION

Building on this motivation, the present paper situates graphic and animated scores within a neurocognitive framework and investigates how they shape performers' mental effort and bodily engagement during performance. It addresses the overarching question: "How do graphic

and animated screen scores shape performers' interpretive decisions, attention, and embodied musical gestures, and how can these effects be articulated as a compositional framework for designing new animated scores?" Sub-questions guiding the empirical inquiry are:

- How do animation parameters, such as shape density, spatial overlap, and timing, affect musicians' cognitive load, stress responses, performance accuracy, and subjective experience?
- Which design features guide or hinder musical expressiveness, clarity, and flow for both professionals and amateurs?

To address these questions, the paper first develops a theoretical framework linking the functions of notation with neurocognitive accounts of conventional and graphic scores and with theories of cognitive and memory load. It then outlines the experimental design of the empirical study and articulates hypotheses that can guide further research on animated notation.

NOTATION

Notation, in its various forms, serves the purpose of communicating artistic ideas from the composer to the performer. *"To notate is also to communicate."* (Rebelo 2010) Different types of notation communicate these ideas using different shapes, some systematic and established, and some abstract and new. Each form of notation also shapes the nature of the composer-performer relationship (Kanga/ Antipolis 2014).

Conventional notation, the most widely recognized system today, employs a standardized set of symbols such as notes, rests, dynamics, and articulations to convey specific musical instructions.

However, conventional notation is not the only method for encoding musical ideas. Most cultures have developed some way of notating their musical ideas, "with each system varying considerably based upon musical and cultural values and societal progress" (Lewis 2010). One example is the Japanese *shō* notation, developed solely for that instrument (Malm 2000). Contrary to the common misconception that graphic notation emerged solely as a contemporary or avant-garde response to conventional conventions, its roots extend back centuries (Lewis 2010).

Graphic notation

Graphic notation designates a range of notational systems that replace or supplement conventional music notation with non-standardized visual elements such as lines, shapes, colors, or spatial arrangements that encode musical parameters (NSW-Government-Australia 2025).

What unifies most forms of graphic notation is the intentional delegation of interpretive agency to the performer, often relying on abstraction, sound-shape correspondences, and multimodal perception.

Graphic notation represents music using minimal or no conventional staff notation, often relying on ambiguous shapes explained through legends or annotations (H. Schroder 2011). "A precise definition of this phenomenon can be elusive, since the very term encompasses a wide range of activity, some of which needs to be related to the broader field of musical *indeterminacy*." (Pace 2007)

The earliest (Western) graphic score is Feldman's "Projection 1" from 1950. "Projection 1" for solo cello uses a unique notation system with three levels representing different timbres (Smith 2016). The 1950s were particularly significant, with influential figures like Earle Brown, John Cage, and Morton Feldman pioneering innovative graphic scores that challenged conventional musical representation (Schroder 2011; Pace 2007). In the 60s and 70s, other composers worked with graphic scores, namely Cornelius Cardew, Mauricio Kagel, Anestis Logothetis, Krzysztof Penderecki and many more (Lewis 2010). Many notation examples can be found in the books by Sauer (Sauer 2009) and Karkoschka (Karkoschka 1966). After the 70s, composers seemed to have lost their interest in graphic scores. In the 20th century, however, graphic notation has seen a "renaissance" (Fischer 2018). With the help of now available technology, many new ways of notating graphically have been invented (Lewis 2010).

Despite all these efforts, a new syntax or a widely recognized shape system has never been established (Fischer 2018). The number and the openness of different graphic notational systems can seem overwhelming for composers and performers, who would rather focus on the conventional notation that they know so well.

Graphic notation today

Since its beginnings in the 1950s, graphic notation has evolved considerably and is now employed not only in contemporary ensemble performances but is also in therapeutic (Bergstrom-Nielsen 1993; Cohen et al. 2011) and educational (Novotna/ Ašenbrennerová, 2021; Reybrouck et al. 2009) settings. Furthermore, these scores facilitate collaboration between classically trained musicians, folk artists, amateurs, and jazz/pop performers through a shared visual language, thereby improving the accessibility of new music (Hope 2020).

Partially because of the availability of technology and the fast spread of information, alternative notational approaches are gaining popularity today. From the

beginning of the 20th century to today, multiple composers have developed Animated Music Notation (AMN), a new form of music notation that uses digital visualization to incorporate movement as a core element of the score. There are many names for this notation, including “Musical Motion Graphics” (Fischer 2018), “screen scores” (Vickery 2012) and “animated music notation” (Smith 2015). Animated scores rely on dynamic visual elements that are essential to their legibility. While some scores adapt conventional notation, most deviate from conventional notation, using graphic scoring techniques (Smith 2016).

Figure 2. Steps of Shape Recognition and Information Processing in Graphic Score Reading.

To systematically address the question of score perception, it is essential to move beyond anecdotal observations and unpack the cognitive and perceptual mechanisms that operate when musicians engage with animated graphic notation. Before detailing the study’s methodology, the following section introduces the proposed three-phase model of shape recognition and information processing in graphic score reading, grounding the experimental design in established neurocognitive theory and offering a clear structure for relating particular score features to measurable performer responses. This integrative model serves as the conceptual bridge between the background context and the empirical strategies used to measure cognitive load, decisionmaking, and gestural action in the empirical study.

STEPS OF SHAPE RECOGNITION AND INFORMATION PROCESSING IN GRAPHIC SCORE READING

Understanding the cognitive demands posed by graphic notation benefits from a neurocognitive perspective grounded in contemporary models of perception, interpretation, and action. Unlike conventional staff notation, which benefits from centuries of standardization, graphic notation introduces abstract, often idiosyncratic visual forms. These require the brain to flexibly integrate and interpret visual information, engaging systems for pattern recognition, sensorimotor mapping, and action planning. Cognitive neuroscience describes perception and action not as a simple serial process but as a set of partially parallel, dynamically interacting stages that transform sensory input into goal-directed behavior. (Eysenck/ Brysbaert 2018: 11) To investigate this complexity, we outline a three-phase model of shape recognition and information processing, conceptually grounded in contemporary neurocognitive theory.

While the field at the intersection of shape perception in human-computer interaction (HCI) and the neurocognitive processing of music notation is still emergent, particularly in relation to graphic notation, recent models offer valuable insights. Building on (Pulvermüller 2023) account of distributed perception–action circuits for shape processing, visual input can be usefully described as unfolding in three phases: perception, transformation, and motor execution. During perception, sensory information is processed within a hierarchical visual system in which bottom-up signals from early visual areas are continuously complemented by top-down influences, reflecting the reciprocal exchange of information throughout the visual hierarchy (Dijkstra et al. 2017). In this context, the performer’s attention and prior experience shape which features of the notation are prioritized and how visually ambiguous configurations are resolved into a particular interpretation. Although the term “three-step perception” is not yet formalized in literature, it provides a useful scaffold for understanding how musicians engage with complex visual stimuli in graphic scores.

Graphic notation systems deviate from the predictable cues of pitch, rhythm, and meter found in conventional scores. Instead, they rely on abstract shape, motion, spatial arrangement, and sometimes interactivity (Henderson 2025). We speculate that this might engage the brain in novel ways, requiring flexible visual perception and imagination.

In visual perception, it is common to distinguish between two general processing modes: bottom-up and top-down (Palmer 1999: 84–85), although this distinction needs refinement in the future (Rauss/ Pourtois 2013). Bottom-up processing begins with small, local details and gradually integrates them into a larger structure, comparable to reading a conventional staff notation note by note and building up a complete musical texture. Top-down processing, in contrast, corresponds to a Gestalt-oriented view: the observer first grasps an overall pattern or image and only subsequently examines the individual components that make it up. Graphic scores usually encourage this latter mode of perception, since performers first encounter them as open, ambiguous images and only gradually develop their sonic realizations from them (Samberg 2015).

Based on these theories, we propose the following phases of graphic score reading:

As performers play the scores they might first *perceive* the global layout, then *process* the graphic details, to *perform* the musical material.

Information intake or **perception** is the initial step in shape interpretation, where the player identifies and processes the visual stimulus. This initial phase activates low-level visual processing as the performer scans and categorizes visual stimuli. In graphic notation, these stimuli may include lines, textures, and movement that afford multiple meanings. As (Lee 2003) suggests, this visual recognition process relies heavily on attention and working memory, especially under time constraints.

Then, the players have to **process** the information, translating the visual information into potential sound. Once perceived, the performer engages in a cognitive-motor process that transforms visual stimuli into imagined sound. This is not a fixed translation but an embodied simulation, a mental rehearsal of gesture and sonority. Barsalou (2008) argues that sensorimotor systems are actively recruited during this stage, forming internal links between what is seen and what might be played. (Barsalou 2008) The performer's experience, musical training, and interaction with the score all shape this mapping process.

Lastly, the processed information has to be translated into **performance**. (Lee 2003) While conventional notation systematization makes it easier to translate the visual input into movement, graphic scores are more complex. Even when only playing conventional notation, a study has indicated that players have restricted cognitive resources when faced with dual-task playing (Çorlu et al. 2014). When reading graphic scores, players need to find their translation systems during the practice and performance

of graphic notation. (Karchkhadze et al. 2024; Sluchin/ Malt 2016).

In the empirical study, this three-phase model directly informed the design of the scores: shape density, spatial overlap, and rotation sensitivity were manipulated to stress each phase differently. We hypothesize that high shape density primarily taxes early perceptual intake by increasing the amount of visual information to be segmented and attended to in a short time window. Spatial overlap between elements might target the transformation phase by forcing performers to resolve figure-ground relationships and map simultaneous shapes onto stable internal representations of musical events. Rotation sensitivity might primarily stress motor execution, because changes in orientation alter how performers plan and execute hand movements on their instruments, even when the underlying visual elements are held constant.

The interviews and questionnaires were constructed to probe the different levels of perception suggested by the model. Separate questions asked the participants about perception, processing and mechanical difficulties, helping us understand the issues in the different levels of perception. Questions about reaction time (time from shape recognition to sound onset) explicitly tap how quickly performers move from visual recognition to imagined sound and executed gesture. Questions on stress, hurry, and the systematicity of their approach capture the subjective cost of maintaining a stable interpretive system under varying score loads. In this way, the model functions not only as a conceptual framework but also as a practical tool for selecting score parameters that either support or deliberately challenge performers' perception and action.

To better understand the study and evaluate its findings, the three-phase model must be situated within broader research on how musicians perceive notation. Most available empirical and neurocognitive work concerns conventional staff notation, which forms the baseline for almost all trained performers. The following section therefore summarizes key mechanisms in conventional music reading, providing a reference point for understanding how and why graphic scores may place different demands on cognition and performance. Those processes are therefore not merely background information but provide reference expectations for efficient score reading that may be disrupted in graphic scores.

NEUROCOGNITIVE PROCESSES INFLUENCING MUSIC PERFORMANCE

Core processes involved in performing conventional music notation, as identified across multiple empirical studies and meta-analyses, include chunking, pattern recognition, hand-eye span, the frequency, and amplitude of eye saccades, audiation, and working memory. (Mishra 2013)

Chunking refers to the cognitive strategy of grouping smaller units of musical information into larger, more manageable patterns, or “chunks” (e.g. melodies, phrases, or rhythmical patterns) (Pike/ Carter 2010). This process allows musicians to process and recall more complex musical information efficiently. While beginners might read note-to-note, experienced players will chunk these together to read and memorize more efficiently (Goolsby 1994; Penttinen/ Huovinen 2011; Zhukov 2014). In the study, chunking is implicitly probed by contrasting scores that present clear, repeated visual groupings through systematic overlap with scores in which high shape density, irregular spacing, and infrequent overlap might make it difficult to form stable visual-musical chunks.

Pattern recognition is a process in which musicians recognize and sometimes predict the course of a melody or harmony based on their experience. Performers often automatically correct mistakes in musical text without even acknowledging them. This demonstrates that not every note in the text is and can be read (Fine et al. 2006). Pattern recognition in graphic scores, especially those that deviate from standardized forms, can be more demanding cognitively, as they lack familiar structures. A study by Arthur (2016) has indicated that adding “*notational features that are unexpected or outside conventional presentation*” interfered with chunking, pattern recognition, and eye movements of participants, making their reactions slower (Arthur et al. 2016). The study probes pattern recognition in graphic notation by reusing the same visual shapes across multiple score versions to examine whether players recognize recurring objects and configurations and, crucially, whether they develop consistent performance strategies for these repeated patterns.

Hand-eye span can be defined as the difference between eye fixation time and finger movement time for a corresponding note, (Kobori/ Takahashi 2008) or as the distance that the eyes are ahead of the hand in playing the piano (Truitt et al. 1997). Expert musicians tend to have a larger hand-eye span that changes size according to phrase length (Fine et al. 2006).

The eye typically shifts around the visual field in rapid movements known as **saccades** about four to five times per second, with each saccade lasting approximately 15 to

50 milliseconds and each fixation (pause) lasting around 150 to 200 milliseconds (Lehmann/ Kopiez 2012). Both hand-eye span and the saccade pattern change with skill and experience (Furneaux/ Land 1999; Waters/ Underwood 1998).

Although eye movements are not measured in the present study, existing work on music reading and visual attention suggests that saccade patterns and fixation behavior would be a particularly promising avenue for future empirical research on graphic and animated notation.

Audiation refers to the ability to mentally “hear” music while reading or performing it, even before it is played on an instrument. Previous research suggests that this process involves musical imagery and is closely related to the act of silently singing the music internally (Brodsky et al. 2008). Audiation can help the performance and sight-reading of musical material (Brodsky et al. 2003). In contrast to conventional scores, which strongly cue pitch, harmony, and meter, graphic notation often provides more ambiguous affordances for audiation, so this mechanism may be less streamlined and more variable across performers. In the first run of the study, this became evident in the striking diversity of interpretations: some participants mapped individual shapes onto specific tonal harmonies, others treated them primarily as articulatory instructions, and still others produced atonal textures or dense clusters that varied mainly in dynamics, articulation, and register.

The amount of information retained in **working memory** during a period of time can be evaluated by experiments that restrict visual access to the score (Lehmann/ Kopiez 2012). It was found that a two-beat preview leads to slower tempos, greater variability in note duration, and increased errors, while optimal performance was achieved with previews of two to four beats or up to the end of the next bar (Truitt et al. 1997). It is also easier to read and remember already known or related information, which could explain why graphic notation, not known to most players, is harder to perform and memorize.

In the study, the experimental manipulations directly probe working memory constraints for animated notation by relating observable error rates, timing stability, and reported stress to score design parameters, especially the number of shapes per second and their degree of overlap. The density and overlap manipulations can be understood as targeted changes in intrinsic and extraneous cognitive load, together predicting higher error rates, greater timing variability, and elevated stress once working memory capacity is exceeded.

It is also important to note that the performer’s training and experience improve all listed interpretive processes.

NEUROCOGNITIVE APPROACHES IN GRAPHIC NOTATION

Alongside this brief review of the cognitive processes involved in conventional music reading, it is essential to examine the neurocognitive mechanisms underlying the interpretation of graphic notation. In this context, where shapes often lack standardized meanings, many musicians may perceive graphic notation merely as abstract visual stimuli. Therefore, this section will focus on shape recognition, cognitive load theory and sound-shape correspondence to examine the neurocognitive processes that happen in the performers' minds.

Figure 3. Excerpt from the piece "The Mind Meld" by the first author. Note the complicated 3D graphic shapes.

Shape recognition

Defined as the process of identifying shapes based on their geometric and spatial relationships, shape recognition relies on dedicated neural assemblies that enable shape-referent mappings, similar to how language and abstract concepts are processed (Pulvermüller 2023). Dehaene et al. suggest that the brain contains multiple "languages of thought" capable of encoding spatial, auditory, and visual structures, implying that graphic score reading may activate overlapping symbolic systems across modalities (Dehaene et al. 2022). These findings support the idea that graphic notation engages a multimodal network of perceptual and cognitive systems, distinct from conventional notation. This multi-modal processing might be one of the causes of the hypothesized increased cognitive load in performers of graphic scores because dividing attention to multiple modes of perception does cause cognitive overload in some cases.

Cognitive load theory

The concept of 7 ± 2 information chunks originates from George Miller's seminal work (Miller 1956), which identifies the typical capacity limit of human short-term memory. However, cognitive load theory (CLT), as developed by John Sweller (Sweller 1988), extends this

concept by focusing on the processing limitations of working memory when engaging with complex information. Together, these frameworks provide a crucial theoretical foundation for understanding how musicians perceive and interpret graphic notation, informing both empirical research and compositional practices.

Cognitive load refers to the mental resources available for problem-solving and task completion, influenced by task complexity, individual differences, and contextual factors. It emphasizes the limitations of attention and working memory in information processing. CLT distinguishes between intrinsic (ICL), extraneous (ECL), and germane (GCL) complexities. Intrinsic cognitive load comes from the inherent complexity of the material and varies based on the learner's prior knowledge. Extraneous cognitive load is caused by poor instructional design or external distractions. Germane cognitive load refers to the effort invested in constructing and refining mental models (Tabatabaee et al. 2024; Wang et al. 2022). CLT research can reduce unnecessary cognitive effort of an interface, or in our case, score design, to optimize task performance (Oviatt 2006), increasing visual complexity raises the risk of errors and reduces efficiency (Kumar/ Kumar 2016; Novak et al. 2017).

CLT suggests that using many or overly complex shapes (ICL) strains the cognitive system, slowing interpretation and increasing fatigue (Oviatt 2006). This may help explain the challenges performers face when engaging with graphic scores, where unfamiliar shapes, lack of formal training, structural ambiguity, and performance pressure converge to create a cognitively demanding experience. This aligns with Miller's finding that working memory can typically hold about 7 ± 2 discrete items (Miller 1956), a capacity that diminishes when information lacks associations with what a person already knows. Because graphic notation is unfamiliar to many performers, they are unable to connect the information, limiting their ability to process more than a few elements at a time.

In the context of the present study, CLT is used less as a strict classification scheme and more as a lens for thinking about how score design pushes performers' limited processing resources. Variations in shape density, spatial overlap, and rotation change how many elements must be processed at once, how easily they can be visually separated, and how straightforward it is to map them onto sound and action. When these demands grow too high, performers are likely to experience increased effort, stress, and loss of precision. Mistakes and timing instabilities in these trials are understood as signs that the available processing resources are saturated. This interpretation is supported by the interview data, where

many participants explicitly reported feeling overloaded or rushed in the denser, more overlapping scores and linked their errors and loss of rhythmic stability to these demands. By systematically varying these parameters and relating them to error patterns, timing stability, and subjective reports, the study begins to show how certain forms of graphic notation may overload the cognitive mechanisms involved in score reading and performance.

Beyond the shape number and overlap, the specific visual forms chosen in graphic notation also matter for how easily performers can map what they see onto what they hear and do.

Sound-shape correspondence

Perception research has revealed systematic links between how shapes look, how sounds are heard, and how they are affectively experienced, a phenomenon best captured by the Bouba–Kiki effect. (Kohler 1929). It indicates that people in all cultures, languages, and writing systems associate soft sounds with round shapes and sharp sounds with spiky ones. This has been observed even in infants, suggesting an innate, possibly evolutionary basis (Fort et al. 2018; Nielsen/ Rendall 2011). Studies suggest that humans instinctively link shapes to sounds and even emotions. Round shapes feel safer and are easier to remember than angular ones (Sonier et al. 2020).

A recent neuroimaging study by Peiffer-Smadja (2019) suggests that the Bouba-Kiki effect activates both auditory and visual sensory cortices, with additional involvement of supra-modal brain areas (regions that process information from multiple sensory modalities). These regions are known for integrating multisensory input and symbolic processing, indicating that sound-shape correspondences may rely on shared neural mechanisms (Peiffer-Smadja/ Cohen 2018).

Pitch metaphor variability

Studies in cross-modal correspondences have shown that people speaking two different languages, Dutch and Farsi, visually perceive pitch differently. While people speaking Dutch or English describe pitch as high and low, the people speaking Farsi or Turkish describe it as thin and thick (Dolscheid et al. 2012; Shayan et al. 2011). These studies indicate that different people connect different meanings, even with simple lines (Dolscheid et al. 2013). These phenomena suggest that some shapes in graphic scores might, after all, have meaning to them and not be completely abstract to the players. The connection of neurocognitive sciences with artistic research and practice could lessen these uncertainties.

Cross-modal correspondences informed the choice of shapes in the experimental scores, enabling an exploration of how simpler versus more conflicting visual metaphors relate to performers' reported strategies, perceived clarity, and sense of expressive freedom. Although these effects are not systematically tested in the current design, the first study run already showed striking diversity in interpretation across a culturally diverse participant group: many performers treated lines as sequences of individual notes, while others interpreted them as glissandi, trills or clusters of varying articulations.

STUDY METHODOLOGY

Having outlined the theoretical background, this section describes the empirical study designed to examine how animated graphic scores affect performers in practice. The methodology translates the proposed neurocognitive and cognitive-load framework into concrete research questions, experimental manipulations, and measurement procedures, providing a basis for interpreting performers' responses in relation to specific notation features.

Research Questions and Hypotheses

The central research question of the study is: *How do graphic scores shape performers' interpretive decisions, attention, and embodied musical gestures, and how can these effects inform a compositional framework for designing new animated scores?*

The research further investigates how animation parameters like shape density, spatial overlap, and rotation sensitivity affect cognitive load, physiological stress, performance accuracy, and subjective experience. It aims to identify which design features guide or hinder musical expressiveness, clarity, and flow, and to derive principles for the future composition of animated screen scores. The main hypothesis is that high visual information density, overlapping shapes, and rotation-sensitive shapes will increase stress responses and error rates by exceeding performers' cognitive capacity. It is further hypothesized that a perceptual threshold exists beyond which performance accuracy and expressive control rapidly deteriorate.

Procedure

All the experiments and interviews were conducted in an identical setting, using the same questionnaires, interview questions, screen size, and researchers. The study took place at the University of Music Karlsruhe (HfM Karlsruhe) in October and December 2025. The environment was

controlled, and all sessions were held in a room free from distractions. Each complete experiment, including the interview, lasted approximately one to one and a half hours per participant.

Before the experiment began, participants were greeted by the researchers and shown into the experiment room, which was equipped with a computer, instruments, a microphone, a camera, and biometric sensors. In the room, the researchers explained the procedure and what the participants could expect. The 3 biometric sensors were then attached to the participants' abdominal area. They were then guided through the experiment via a presentation displayed on the computer screen.

The experiment evaluated participants' performances using 12 graphic scores of varying difficulty. One conventionally notated score was included to establish a baseline cognitive response for each participant. The 12 graphic scores were generated by a Python program and remained identical for all participants to facilitate consistent data analysis and visualization. This design enabled direct comparison of MIDI, touch sensor, and physiological data across participants and between individual performances and the notated materials.

Figure 4. A participant playing a score during the experiment.

To mitigate familiarization effects, the scores were presented in a randomized order. The familiarization effect referred to the potential bias whereby the first score might appear more challenging, while later scores could seem easier as participants became more accustomed to the animated notation. To further reduce this effect, a trial score consisting of shapes different from those used in the study was introduced at the beginning of each session. Participants were also provided a

reference sheet of all shapes before the experiment began and were given two to three minutes to familiarize themselves with the visual vocabulary.

Study Design

The study employed a mixed-methods convergent design to investigate how animated graphic scores influenced performer cognition, interpretation, and physiology. In a convergent design, quantitative and qualitative data were collected simultaneously. Interactive procedures were used, whereby already collected and analyzed data informed subsequent data collection methods (Creswell/Clark 2017). Quantitative and qualitative data were gathered in parallel, including biometric signals, MIDI-based performance data, subjective self-reports, and interviews. This design enabled triangulation and cross-validation of findings, offering both depth and breadth in understanding the impact of animated score parameters on performance.

Rooted in cognitive load theory, the study examined how shape density, overlap, and rotation affected interpretive decisions, cognitive effort, and physiological responses.

By integrating qualitative insights and biometric data, the approach addressed both objective performance measures and the lived experience of musicians interpreting graphic notation systems.

Participants in the first round

Adults ($n = 18$) without visual or hearing impairments were recruited. A pre-screening registration questionnaire ensured alignment with the target profile. Most participants were recruited personally. The study did not aim for population generalizability but rather for depth of insight into a specific musician demographic. Years of active playing ranged from roughly 10 to over 30 years, with a central tendency around 20–25 years of experience. The first run included participants from a total of 13 countries across the European, Asian, and Australian continents. All participants provided written consent for their participation, the collection of data, and any potential publication. Since musical response was influenced by experience, all participants were professionals with significant expertise on their instrument, as determined by the registration questionnaire that all had to complete.

The participants were furthermore asked about their experience with classical and new music as well as graphic and animated scores. All participants were highly experienced in conventionally notated classical and new music while having less experience in graphic and especially animated notation.

Materials

Figure 5. Screenshot from Score 3: Lines only

To ensure the study is both reproducible and analytically rigorous, the experimental scores were organized into three main conditions based on shape type and structural complexity:

- Rotation-Sensitive (Lines)
- Rotation-Insensitive (Quatrefoils)
- Mixed (Three Shape Types with Varying Rotation Sensitivity)

Each condition included four scores that systematically varied in two key parameters: *shape density* and the presence or absence of *overlap*.

The densities were:

- Low density: 15 shapes
- High density: 30 shapes

The overlap condition was binary:

- Non-overlapping: all shapes were clearly separated in both horizontal (time) and vertical (pitch) space, with no visual or temporal intersection.
- Overlapping: at least three shapes overlap at least three times during the score.

In the mixed condition, three different shapes were combined: arcs (highly rotation-sensitive), triangles (moderately rotation-sensitive), and starbursts (not rotation-sensitive). Distribution was kept balanced by the inclusion of 5 shapes of each type in low-density scores and 10 each in high-density ones.

This yielded a total of 12 scores:

- Lines (Rotation is Relevant)
 - Score 1: Low density, non-overlapping
 - Score 2: Low density, overlapping
 - Score 3: High density, non-overlapping
 - Score 4: High density, overlapping
- Quatrefoils (Rotation Is Not Relevant)
 - Score 5: Low density, non-overlapping
 - Score 6: Low density, overlapping
 - Score 7: High density, non-overlapping
 - Score 8: High density, overlapping
- Mixed (Arcs, Triangles, Starbursts)

- Score 9: Low density, non-overlapping
- Score 10: Low density, overlapping
- Score 11: High density, non-overlapping
- Score 12: High density, overlapping

Figure 6. Screenshot from Score 12: Arcs, Triangles, Starbursts. Overlapping, high density score.

This refined structure had allowed for controlled comparison across four variables: shape type, overlap, density, and rotation. Shape thickness was kept constant across all scores to eliminate it as a confounding variable. By systematically balancing these across all twelve scores, the study was able to isolate the effects of each factor.

Additionally, each score fully utilized the display area, ensuring consistent spatial layout and reducing confounding factors such as blank space or underutilized screen regions.

1. Registration Questionnaire

Before the experiment, participants completed a registration questionnaire that gathered background, musical experience, and attitudes toward graphic notation.

2. After-score Questionnaire

After each score, participants completed a brief questionnaire about perceived difficulty, stress, anxiety, and other impressions. At the session's end, a standardized semistructured interview captured strategies, specific difficulties, and participant feedback.

2. Please rate your overall experience with this score:

○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○

☹️ 😊

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3. How difficult did you find this score?

To read

Easy ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ Difficult

To perform

Easy ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ Difficult

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4. Did you feel lost at any point during the performance?

If yes, please elaborate when and/or why (e.g. specific symbol, action or gesture)

Yes

No

Figure 7. The Beginning of the After-Score Questionnaire.

3. Interviews

Directly after the experiments, researchers conducted standardized interviews. The participants were asked to openly talk about each score and rate the scores' difficulty. Afterward, they were asked the following questions:

- How did you feel while interpreting and playing the scores?
- What strategy did you use to translate the visual shapes into sound?
- Did you feel stressed while playing?
- Did any aspects of the scores make interpretation or performance especially difficult?
- If you could change something in the scores to make them easier or more intuitive to play, what would it be?

Equipment and Data Collection

Participants performed on a Yamaha Disklavier piano fitted with TouchKeys sensors to record fine hand movement details, or on a Sylphyo wind controller that captured notes, air intensity, and timing. Physiological data were collected using Noraxon heart rate and respiration sensors placed according to manufacturer guidelines. Video, MIDI, Touchkeys and audio were recorded on a MacBook running Max MSP MuBu, and all data streams were synchronized using an audio-based sync pulse created by participants before each trial.

Figure 8. Study setup at the SAM•ComputerStudio

Ethical Considerations

Informed consent was obtained for all procedures. Data were anonymized, videos were blurred for any dissemination, and confidentiality was strictly maintained. No invasive procedures or excessive stress were involved; standard university insurance applied. All data were stored locally and securely with restricted researcher access.

Limitations

The sample, especially in the first round only, is small and consists only of professional musicians, suggesting that

the results may not generalize to amateur players or children; future studies should examine these effects in those populations. A specific type of a score is used in the study, so the findings may not apply to all forms of notation, especially given the large variation in animated graphic score design. Biometric measures are indirect proxies for cognitive load and should therefore be interpreted in conjunction with behavioral and self-report data.

PRELIMINARY RESULTS

Preliminary results presented herein are based on the integration of qualitative data from interviews and questionnaires collected during the first run of the study, supplemented by the author's reflective commentary. The results are therefore not final with detailed analysis of biometric and MIDI data planned for 2026.

From the registration questionnaire, some general attitudes about graphic notation can be summarized. The participants generally described graphic notation in a balanced, rather positive way, but almost always as something complementary to, and not replacing, traditional notation. Several comments say graphic scores are "good for certain aspects", "interesting", or "not bad" and emphasize that they can show actions on the instrument or allow more freedom and improvisation than traditional notation. Participants mention enjoying the liberty to interpret more freely and seeing graphic scores as a good avenue when one wants more creative agency or to work outside normal notational parameters. One person states liking both systems and not wanting to choose between them.

At the same time, it was mentioned that graphic notation is bad at representing precise note values and that conventional notation is better for accuracy and is more familiar. Some say they personally still prefer conventional notation or find graphic scores too "nonbinding," implying a desire for clearer structure and rules.

Questionnaire overview

Across all scores, the mean general response was 5.21 on a scale from 1 (most negative) to 7 (most positive), indicating an overall favorable affective evaluation. Very low ratings were rare, whereas high ratings were common, with one-fourth selecting the maximum value of 7. Most responses were at or above the midpoint, suggesting that participants generally experienced the scores as positive rather than negative.

Overlapping, high-density scores (score 8 and score 12) received the least positive affective responses, with both

scores receiving a lower mean general response rating ($M = 4$) on the 1–7 scale. This pattern suggests that shape density and overlap may reduce performers’ affective engagement with the material, even when the same shapes are used in less dense configurations. Therefore, not only the type of notation but also its spatial organization appears to play a key role in shaping performers’ overall evaluation of the scores.

Figure 9. Responses were skewed toward the positive end of the scale.

Overall, participants reported a moderate level of stress and time pressure while reading the scores. The scores 8 and 12, which received the lowest overall ratings, also produced relatively higher stress. Additionally, score 12 was associated with the strongest feeling of being rushed. In contrast, less dense scores with similar symbolic material like score 1, score 5, and score 9, were associated with lower stress and hurry ratings while simultaneously achieving higher affective evaluations.

Qualitative impressions

The questionnaire findings aligned closely with the qualitative interviews, in which several recurring patterns emerged in participants’ descriptions of their experience with the scores.

1. General affective response

Across interviews, the first 18 respondents described the playing task as enjoyable, playful, and musically engaging, often comparing it to a game or experimental improvisation rather than to conventional score reading. Participants reported elevated stress relative to their usual performance situations, but some explicitly framed this as a specific form of cognitive strain, resembling a state in which “the brain has too many things to do at one time” rather than performance anxiety in the narrow sense. It was also mentioned that this stress was fun, similar to the stress of playing a game.

Participants consistently identified segments with many shapes in a very short time as the most demanding, even though the physical tempo of the animation was constant

across conditions. These passages were experienced as faster because reduced preview and processing time increased moment-to-moment decision pressure, consistent with the notion of elevated cognitive load rather than with an objective tempo increase.

2. Shapes

Aligning vertical screen position with pitch height, analogous to traditional notation, placing higher shapes in higher registers and lower shapes in lower registers was frequently reported.

Shape size was often mapped to loudness, note number, and duration, with larger shapes associated with higher dynamic levels and more notes and smaller shapes with shorter or quieter realizations. The tendency to align vertical position with pitch and size with dynamics or note number shows that performers quickly imposed familiar cross-modal metaphors and conventional score habits on the novel notation, effectively creating chunks and anchors that reduce interpretive effort.

Several participants mentioned that they largely forgot to plan articulation, even though they produced varied articulations automatically during performance. This suggests that articulation was not a primary focus of their explicit mapping strategies.

Overlapping shapes were repeatedly described as particularly challenging. Pianists reported situations where there were “more shapes than hands”, while wind-instrument players noted the impossibility of realizing notated “clusters” that implied multiple simultaneous pitches. In both cases, simultaneity forced prioritization or reduction strategies and was cited as a principal source of overload.

Some participants reported being stressed by a large variety of different shapes occurring together, whereas others reported stress when many identical shapes appeared simultaneously. Certain shapes, especially the multi-circle figure, were perceived as semantically undetermined, affording many possible realizations and thus increasing interpretive uncertainty. When large numbers of such shapes appeared together, participants reported feeling visually and conceptually overwhelmed.

3. Exposure

With ongoing exposure, participants described a transition to feelings of calmness, familiarity, and greater enjoyment, suggesting they quickly adapted to the representational system. One individual, however, noted that their self-imposed expectations became more demanding toward the end of the experiment, which led to increased stress.

4. Translation systems

Most performers assigned each shape type to a characteristic gesture or harmony. These mappings ranged from pitch-specific chord progressions, through atonal melodies and clusters to particular articulations, but in all cases they functioned as stable interpretive rules. It was mentioned that they changed the rules throughout the experiment, with some saying they could not follow their rules anymore due to the score density and overlap. Again, overlap and density emerged as the primary factors that disrupted the application of otherwise well-defined translation schemes. Participants stated that recognizing the shapes was unproblematic but that processing and executing the corresponding musical actions within the available time was difficult.

5. Results

Preliminary data suggests that participants rarely struggled to recognize the shapes themselves, indicating that basic perceptual intake remained intact even under demanding conditions. Instead, reported problems clustered around “falling behind,” losing track of their translation systems, and feeling unsure what to play, which points to overload in the transformation and motor execution phases rather than in low-level recognition.

The descriptions of overlapping and dense passages as “faster” despite constant animation tempo suggest that reduced preview time compressed all three phases, forcing perception, mapping, and action planning to occur almost simultaneously. This aligns with the three-step model’s expectation that when the temporal window for sequential perception – transformation – execution collapses, subjective time pressure and error likelihood increase. The frequent need to abandon or simplify self-defined translation systems in dense, overlapping scores indicates that working memory capacity for maintaining rules and current visual input was exceeded.

The partial shift from initial stress to later calmness and enjoyment with repeated exposure suggests that experience allowed performers to reconfigure their strategies so that the same visual input generated more stable, chunked interpretations, thereby lowering effective cognitive load. At the same time, the fact that one participant reported rising stress due to growing self-expectations underlines that internal performance standards can re-inflate cognitive load even as perceptual familiarity increases

Overall, the preliminary results support the theoretical claim that animated graphic scores are not inherently more difficult than conventional notation; rather, difficulty arises where design choices push one or more

phases of the perception–transformation–execution chain beyond working memory limits. High density, simultaneity, and shape ambiguity jointly increase cognitive load by multiplying and destabilizing real-time mapping decisions, whereas intuitive visual metaphors, consistent translation systems, and repeated exposure support learning, expressivity, and a playful, game-like engagement with the notation.

RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS AND OPPORTUNITIES

Taken together, the three phases of perception, the study and the preliminary reflection provide a practical lens for both composing and performing animated graphic scores. The preliminary findings suggest that such research can help identify which visual or structural features of a score are most cognitively demanding, ultimately contributing to the development of more performer-friendly compositional strategies.

The reality of (animated) graphic score performance is that the combination of unfamiliar visual language, shape density, overlap, and internal performance pressure may increase performers’ cognitive load. In practice, this can translate into moments of uncertainty, disorientation, or hesitation about what or how to play. At the same time, remarks gathered during the study indicate that performers often experience this uncertainty not only as a challenge but also as a source of engagement and enjoyment.

Educational research has shown that graphic notation encourages ensemble performance, creative thinking and accessible music making (McKenna 2011), these preliminary observations point to a similar pattern among professional musicians. What may initially appear as “problems” in graphic scores can, in fact, be reframed as creative opportunities. For professional musicians, the interpretive ambiguities and open-endedness of such scores seem to prompt greater decision-making, collaboration, and imaginative thinking, often resulting in highly creative and innovative performances.

During the first phase of the study, it was striking how much enjoyment participants expressed while performing the scores, as well as the diversity of interpretative approaches they adopted. These performances demonstrated that, although graphic notation can pose interpretive difficulties for performers at any level, it strongly encourages exploration and inventiveness, qualities central to artistic development. While it is important to show how graphic notation influences professional musicians, we feel that it is important to state

how important this approach is for children and amateurs as well.

Graphic scores and music visualizations can serve to represent existing musical pieces or to encourage children to make their own music (Miletic/ Vukicevic, 2013). Some educators have even developed new graphic notation systems for various purposes: some are haptic systems specifically designed for people with visual impairments (Karpodini/ Michailidis, 2022), and others are based on color codes made to make harmony learning easier (Klemenc et al. 2011). Furthermore, some educators have created instrument-specific graphic notation systems (Romana 2023) that have been very well received by the children using them (Nikolaou et al. 2024). Music visualization has been successfully used in educational projects with children and adults of all ages, including preschool children (Vidulin/ Zi zovic 2024).

Case study

The study of participatory and inclusive practices in music mediation (Stibi 2023; Wild 2023) has gained importance recently, an example of which is the collaborative project between the first author, Dr. Cornelia Wild, a concert hall in Baden-Baden, the Karlsruhe University of Music (HfM), and the sixth grade of a school in Karlsruhe (Germany), during which school students created their own graphic scores that they played at the renowned concert hall. This project's goal was to enable school students to create compositions and play them in an ensemble with professional musicians, therefore introducing them to the world of classical music without the costly conventional music lessons that they cannot afford. Our approach to this was the following: students listened to short excerpts from "Livre pour Cordes" by Pierre Boulez and were invited to visually transcribe the musical events using lines, dots, and squiggles. They then improvised music based on their visual drawings. Even at this early stage, the results were musically rich, and the students enjoyed the improvisational process. Both the professional musicians and the children were able to read from the score, confirming the earlier speculations about the inclusivity of graphic notation.

In the next session, they were given melodic instruments and followed the graphics again, but this time each child developed their own graphics for their sounds. They understood this well, some creating graphic notation for motor noises or beatboxing, sounds that would be difficult or impossible to notate using conventional notation. Scores were created and played by an ensemble made of children and students from HfM Karlsruhe, showing that graphic notation truly does enable interdisciplinary projects that would be exceptionally difficult using any other notational system.

During the workshops with students at the Anne-Frank Schule, we observed an unexpected trend: participants, particularly those without formal musical training, initially struggled more with simple graphic scores composed of simple shapes, like lines, than with denser, more complex instructions. The lack of referential anchors or contextual cues in the minimalist designs appeared to cause hesitation and confusion. However, as the students began creating their own graphic notations and integrated these personal systems into the simpler scores, their understanding, and confidence noticeably improved. Over time, the scores became increasingly complex, often incorporating layered shapes, but were paradoxically easier for the students to interpret and perform. This suggests that personal shape construction, even when it leads to higher visual density, may reduce cognitive load by leveraging internalized meaning and emotional association.

Figure 10. A graphic score produced during the project.

Other benefits

The preliminary results and the case study underpin the importance of tackling graphic notation with both professional and amateur musicians, and its introduction into the curriculum of schools and universities. We are convinced that by fostering knowledge in this field and making knowledge easily accessible, graphic scores will become more approachable and relevant and may facilitate expanded and new means of expression.

Beyond their clear pedagogical and inclusive potential, graphic scores offer additional benefits that merit closer attention. In her own artistic practice, the first author observed a marked increase in audience engagement when graphic notation is either projected during performances or made interactive for spectators. These observations align with current research on media consumption habits, indicating that the prevalence of digital and multimedia content, particularly on social media platforms, has significantly altered attention spans and perceptual preferences (Carr 2010). Audiences today often struggle to engage with purely auditory or purely visual stimuli in the absence of multimedial or interactive components (Parry/ Roux 2018).

Therefore, presenting music within a multimedia framework that is visually intelligible to the audience can enhance cognitive and emotional engagement and help the audience understand the otherwise hidden processes in an ensemble or computer-based performance (Fox 2016). This approach not only increases the appeal of contemporary concert experiences but also makes them more accessible to younger generations, many of whom express a diminished interest in conventional classical concert formats due to a perceived lack of immersive or stimulating elements. Although this change may reflect broader sociocultural changes in entertainment consumption, it also opens new possibilities for revitalizing classical music. One could then say that the use of graphic notation, especially in the multimedial context, is a promising tool for adapting classical music performance to 21st-century audiences, thereby expanding its cultural reach and contemporary relevance. Building on these observations, the following conclusions draw together the core findings of this study regarding the educational and artistic value of graphic notation and its potential to reshape both performance and pedagogy.

CONCLUSIONS

Ultimately, it was found that graphic scores are not inherently more difficult than conventional notation. Difficulties emerge when construction parameters push visual complexity, density, and overlap beyond what can be efficiently perceived, transformed, and executed, so that compositional choices themselves become a source of cognitive overload. At the same time, the neurocognitive processes used for conventional notation do not always transfer to these scores, and the lack of systematic education in alternative notational practices further amplifies this difficulty. Yet participants also reported experiencing this heightened cognitive demand as a form of “positive stress”, with many describing the scores as stimulating and rewarding to play.

Scores 12 and 8, which combined high density with substantial overlap, received the lowest overall ratings and were consistently described as feeling faster and overly stressful, with some shapes effectively becoming unplayable. Participants’ qualitative reports confirmed the quantitative findings, characterizing these scores as playful and creatively engaging yet distinctly taxing in passages of high density, in line with the proposed three-phase perception model and the cognitive-load perspective.

Stepping back, it is also important to mention that the pedagogical and creative potential of graphic scores is considerable. Their visual design is tweakable depending

on the wished cognitive load and creative openness, making them ideal for facilitating collective, interdisciplinary work that would be difficult to do using conventional notation. When written for professional musicians, graphic scores can open up new sound worlds and allow more creative freedom, all while keeping the audiences engaged. An awareness of the mentioned neurocognitive processes of score reading can assist the composer in creating scores that are more cognitively aware and performantly efficient.

Finally, instead of being viewed as problems, the complexities and intellectual challenges of graphic notation can be viewed as opportunities for richer investigation, broadened pedagogy, and artistic inventiveness.

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[Abstract in Korean | 국문 요약]

그래픽 기보와 사고: 그래픽 악보 연주의 인지적, 심리적, 생리적 메커니즘

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이 논문은 악보 인지, 인지부하 이론, 기호 인식, 교차양상 인식 분야에서의 연구결과를 바탕으로, 그래픽 악보를 읽는데 관련된 신경인지학적 메커니즘을 이해하기 위한 이론적인 토대를 제시한다. 그림 혹은 애니메이션 악보를 보고 연주하는 인지적 모델을 제안하면서, 어떻게 악보가 연주자의 해석적 판단과 집중, 신체적 동작에 영향을 미치게 되는지 분석한다. 생체반응과 행동, 질적인 측정 결과들을 종합하여 개발중인 혼합방법 연구를 이용하여, 다양하게 변화하는 시각적 복잡함과 공간 배치, 동작 타이밍이 체계적으로 조작된 악보에 연주자가 어떻게 반응하는지 조사한다.

연구 결과에 따르면 그래픽 악보가 기존의 기보법에 비해 반드시 어려운 것은 아니다. 오히려, 어려움은 악보 각 요소의 시각적 복잡함과 밀도, 중첩 등이 연주자의 인지 능력을 벗어날 때 생긴다. 초기 연구 결과에 따르면 악보의 높은 밀도와 중첩은 스트레스와 오류 확률을 증가시키지만, 참가자들은 하나같이 좌절감보다 긍정적이고 창의적인 업무로 인식하는 경향을 보였다. 사례 연구는 그래픽 기보가 포용성과 창의성을 증진시키고, 기존의 기보법의 장벽 없이 연주를 가능케하며, 특히 어린이나 아마추어 음악가에게 유용하다는 점을 입증한다. 이 글은, 작곡 및 교육 실습을 동반한 신경인지 연구를 종합함으로써, 그래픽 기보가 단순한 예술적 표현일 뿐 아니라 학제간 연구와 교육적 혁신의 범위로 여겨야 하며, 현대 음악교육과 연주 활성화를 위한 잠재력이 있음을 주장한다.

주제어: 그래픽 기보, 악보 인지, 신경인지, 그래픽 악보 연주.

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